

THE LIFE SPAN OF THE MILITARY OFFICER IN TURKEY

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Abstract:

In this study it is attempted to get a notion about the average life span of officers in Turkey. Ten random issues of The Journal of the Association of Retired Officers are employed for this purpose. The last pages of the mentioned journal are devoted to obituary notices, where names, military branches and decease dates are entered. The military record or registry (numéro d'inscription / Regisriernummer) of each is also included and this is the critical knowledge, since the number provides the graduation dates, from which the birth date is easily calculated. The average officer lives a decade longer than the country's average-male citizen.

Keywords:

Officer, life span, obituary notice, birth date, death date.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The officer's record consists of two hyphenated numbers, the first of which is the graduation-and-commission date. The second number reflects the academic standing: The more successful the graduate as far as his cumulative course average is concerned; the smaller is the second number.

In this research mostly the graduates of the War Colleges come into account. The War College automatically denotes the army's officer source. It is the equivalent of America's West Point. Gendarme officers come from the same source. The Naval War College is the equivalent of Annapolis Naval academy in Maryland. Finally the Air War College can be regarded as the equivalent of the United States Air Force academy located at Colorado Springs.

Data regarding officers with civilian university education like military medical doctors or veterinary surgeons or engineers or teachers, are at a minimum. To avoid some possible confusion; let us specify that engineering corps or fortifications is a combat-support-branch of the army, whose members come from the War College. Topographical engineers also come from the War College and later undergo various professional courses. A few Topographical engineers were present within the data.

2. METHODOLOGY

At a second-hand bookstore I ran into a bunch of journals. There were thirteen of them all together. I was long familiar with the journal, anyway. It is the publication of the Association of

Retired Officers. Thumbing through the pages, the idea occurred to me right away. For no other profession one could find so regular and detailed data revealing the life spans.

Those journals contained a good bunch of data to be evaluated and I bought them immediately, without even bargaining (as it is conventional to bargain at such a store). Indeed, Chang (2008: 47-48) [1] (by reference to Ellis & Bochner 2000: 739-740) tells us that a wide array of labels indicating an auto-ethnographic (*) orientation includes [among others] items like first-person accounts, impressionistic accounts and even opportunistic research [as long as complying with ethics, as I feel to add]. No offence, on my part! One might as well go ahead and label all that work an opportunistic research.

At home at a closer glance it was discovered that three issues were repeated among the bunch of journals, which left us with only ten distinct copies.

The obituary notices got scanned. Each journal was assigned a code name arbitrarily, to facilitate the work. The codes went as ZABİT 01 [6], ZABİT 02 [7] etc. (“Zabit” is the older, Ottoman word for “officer”).

Then the life span of each officer was easily calculated and listed together. The War Colleges (for Land, Navy and Air Force) used to be at the level of 2-year-long junior Colleges, regarding the duration of higher education. (1972 graduates had 3-year-schooling; 1978 graduates were the first generation to have 4-year-schooling). Physicians had 6 years of university history, veterinary surgeons had 5 and engineers four. Those branches’ birth dates were calculated accordingly.

Some of the entries are about females, the crushing majority of whom are officers’ wives. A few are officers’ daughters. There are also civilians who were honorary members of the society. All those entries are excluded for our purposes.

At the Appendix of this paper all scanned pages as well as the tabulations are shown.

How Good are the Data in Reflecting Birth Dates?

Students who interrupt schooling are not admitted to military schools. Therefore, all cadets are at the specified, proper age in admission date. The Military Education Institutions find their “footing” from among sheer middle classes. Most are urban youths, even if from the provinces. This fact alone ensures that their birth dates were duly registered.

* The explanation of auto-ethnography makes it transcend autobiography by connecting the personal to the cultural. The importance of linking the self and the social is also affirmed in Reed-Danahay’s influential book, *Auto / Ethnography: Rewriting the Self and the Social*, 1997 (paraphrased from Chang 2008: 46) [1].

In villages, births were not as soundly reported as in town centers, at least in former years. A peasant cannot go to the Population Registry Department in the district immediately and delays do occur. Some deliberately postpone the baby-registries. A daughter should appear younger at her wedding. A boy may thus get drafted into the compulsory military service (as a private / plain soldier) at an age somewhat older than twenty, in order to suffer the hardships (*) better.

Some of the officers had failed one or more courses and had to repeat the whole year. But they are only a tiny percent of the officer-population. Usually in a classroom comprising roughly thirty military students at most one or two are “washbacks” from a previous year, and they carry different cadet-numbers on their collars.

Many cadets do fail in difficult courses (namely science courses like Math, Physics or Chemistry) in June at the end of the year. However; following a summer course, they eventually pass the September conditional exams, in practice, in accordance with the long traditions and conventions.

As an army major (September 15, 2014) explained to me in Ankara; while a cadet at the military lycée in Bursa, their officer-in-charge of disciplinary issues was famous” for having lost three (!) years in his educative history, as an exception. One year in military junior high school (**), another year in military high school and still another year in War College. (Loosing two years in one of those stages means dismissal). I remembered the name (M.K.) from my own military service days. But I learned this secret of his only recently. The mentioned individual had a brilliant professional career as an infantry officer.

It is probable that university graduates had failed at least one year or maybe more. There courses are harder, after all. In former times, one could stay in Turkish universities until graduation, as a rule of thumb. A military student who keeps the title of student automatically keeps his title of military student (following studies on the account of the military).

A teacher-colonel in *Çankırı*, years ago, mentioned about his eccentric classmate at the Faculty of Turcology. “This fellow” had deliberately failed an easy course —thereby not jeopardizing his eventual graduation— successively, in order to prolong his military student life. Food, clothing and sleeping wards and the humble pocket money paid to cadets kept him happy as a student, instead of graduating, getting a rank and assuming many responsibilities. This is an exceptional case, as well.

* Kışlalı (1967: 155) [2] asserts that the Turkish Johnny leads a rather hard life with his shaven head —ever since mid 1990s plain soldiers are allowed to have some hair— a single official clothing and mediocre collective meals. But he does not mind it. Most of them are deprived even of those conditions back home in their villages and small towns, anyhow.

** There were two junior military high schools, one in Istanbul-*Selimiye* district, the other in *Erzincan*. They got abolished in late-1960s.

3. RESULTS

Processing the data from ten issues of the The Journal of the Association of Retired Officers verified the fact that the average life span of the officer in Turkey is 81.1 years. This is quite a high value.

4. DEBATE AND CONCLUSION

“Life-expectancy is a very useful standard measure for comparing the health of societies, and for noting progress and regress in economic development. In Norway in 2000 it was 79 years and in the USA 77 years. In Sierra Leone it was 35 years. As an example of regress we can note that for Russia, life-expectancy fell between 1986-94 from 70 to 64 years” (Bruce & Yearley, 2006: 173) [3].

In Turkey, on the average, women live 78 years while men live only 71 years (Hürriyet Newspaper, 16.12.2013) [4]. It should be no surprise that the average officer outlives the average male citizen (81.1 years versus 71 years). The health examinations at the entrance to the military schools ensure that the population-samples constituting the officers are at good health, initially. Moreover they lead disciplined lives, including sportive activities and they are fairly well-to-do, in terms of their gains (fairly good salaries with respect to other government employees). Another factor can be their relatively high IQ points, when the immense competition to enter the military schools is considered. Out of roughly thirty thousand applicants to military high schools about a thousand are accepted.

After all; Lewis Madison Terman’s (1877-1956) famous longitudinal research starting in 1920s on hundreds of gifted Californian school children showed that they were more successful, more adaptable and healthier in the long run, than other Americans. “Even the death rate was about 33 percent lower than that for the general population (Sprinthall & Sprinthall, 1990: 445) [5].

5. REFERENCES

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- [7] Birlik Dergisi [The Journal of Unity] No.195, Ankara: TESUD [the Association of Retired Officers] publication, January-February-March 2012.

- [8] *Birlik Dergisi [The Journal of Unity] No.172, Ankara: TESUD [the Association of Retired Officers] publication, November-December 2007.*
- [9] *Birlik Dergisi [The Journal of Unity] No.196, Ankara: TESUD [the Association of Retired Officers] publication, April-May-June 2012.*
- [10] *Birlik Dergisi [The Journal of Unity] No.194, Ankara: TESUD [the Association of Retired Officers] publication, October-November-December 2011.*
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APPENDIX

VISUAL SUPPLEMENT

Fig.1. In Karacaahmet Cemetery in Istanbul, the grave of a retired infantry colonel (Em. P. Alb.) next to that of a Major (Bnb.) (Photo by the Author—S.Ç.)

Fig.2. A Gendarmarie station in the city of *Tekirdağ*. Gendarmarie officers cope with criminal activities in rural areas (Photo by the Author—S.Ç.)

Fig. 3. Again in *Karacaahmet* Cemetery, the grave of a retired staff officer at the rank of “*tuğbay*”. Year of death is marked as 1967. That special rank between colonel and brigadier-general used to be issued in early Republican era and got abolished afterwards. (Photo by the Author—S.Ç.)

Fig. 4. Cardboard drinking cups with the logos of the Second and the Fifth Armycorps, respectively. (Scanned by the Author—S.Ç.)

DETAILED DATA AS BASIS FOR CALCULATIONS

The First Journal: Issue Number 197, July-August-September 2012			
Officer's Branch	Initials (Name)	Age at Death	Explanations if Required (Crushing majority are colonels, some have lower ranks like LT-Col or Major)
Quartermaster (Supplies)	B.Ş.S.	78	
Infantry	N.S.	79	
Infantry	o.ü.	86	
Personnel Officer	H.Y.	84	
Artillery	M.F.T.	93	
Gendarme	Y.E.	67	
Air Force Pilot	S.Y.	78	
GENERAL (*)	N.T.	91	One-Star-General
STAFF OFFICER	E.K.K.	82	
Gendarme	M.N.	85	
Ordnance	R.B.	81	
	Y.K.E.	90	Senior Colonel from Şişli; Branch unidentified
Artillery	V.T.	89	
Quartermaster	M.T.E.	91	

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Artillery	A.C.S.	90	
Veterinary Surgeon	T.G.	85	Record: 1950-15 (5 years of higher schooling)
Military Judge	H.Ö.	81	Record: 1953-12 (4 years of higher schooling)
Air Force Quartermaster	B.C.Ç.	78	
Air Force Pilot	C.G.	75	
Infantry	M.E.	81	
Personnel Officer	H.T.E.	88	
Air Force Finance Officer	A.Ş.	85	Finance branch got instigated in early 1980s. They were transferred from the Quartermaster branch.
Infantry	M.F.Y.	71	
Infantry	M.Y.	93	
Infantry	A.R.İ.	85	
	B.K.		Colonel from Bolu. Branch unidentified. Record Number and accordingly age is also unidentified.
Artillery	Ş.Ş.	91	
Signals	M.Ş. İ.	91	
NAVY	M.G.	69	1963-Graduate (There are no graduates of Ground Forces at this date due to May 21 incidents).
Medical Doctor	M.E.T.	82	Record: 1954-55 (6 years of higher schooling)
Infantry	M.N.D.	80	
	A.K.	91	Senior Colonel from Çankaya; Branch unidentified
Infantry	A.D.	78	
Pilot	E.B.	81	(Whether Ground Forces or Air Force Pilot is unidentified.
Infantry	H.K.D.	72	
Tank	C.G.	90	
GENERAL (*)	A.A.	88	One-Star-General
STAFF OFFICER	E.U.	75	
Quartermaster	F.Ö.	79	
	A.U.	76	Branch unidentified. Rank is captain, which could only mean retired due to disability.
Air Force Ground Officer	A.C.A.	91	

END of the First Journal. Out of 52 obituary notices one was an honorary civilian member; 10 were officers' wives. Net number of entries is 41. 82.8 is the average of this table.

The 2nd Journal: Issue Number 195, January-February-March 2012

Officer's Branch	Initials (Name)	Age at Death	Explanations if Required (Crushing majority are colonels, some have lower ranks like LT-Col or Major)
Air Force Ground Officer	M.Ş.	76	
GENERAL (**)	M.S.	88	Two-Star-General

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	C.D.	62	Senior Colonel from Bornova; Branch unidentified
Infantry	M.N.A.	83	
Gendarme	A.Y.	85	
Tank	A.N.E.	90	
Personnel Officer	C.K.	76	
	F.M.	77	Senior Colonel from Konak; Branch unidentified
Gendarme	M.Ç.	76	
	B.S.E.	90	Senior Colonel from Beyoğlu; Branch unidentified
Medical Doctor	M.A.C.	83	Record: 1952-32 (6 years of higher schooling)
Artillery	A.N.Ç.	88	
(Ground Force) Pilot	M.C.Ö.	88	
Transportation	F.T.	86	
Tank	F.Ö.	85	
STAFF (of Infantry)	İ.S.P.	86	
Air Force STAFF	A.D.	85	
Air Force Ground Officer	Y.F.O.	78	
STAFF (of Artillery)	H.S.	80	
ADMIRAL (**)	M.C.B.	93	Two-Star-Admiral
Air Force Ground Officer	V.T.	91	
Quartermaster	S.S.	81	
STAFF (of Artillery)	H.M.G.	91	
Infantry	C.E.	84	
Tank	B.A.	66	
Quartermaster	İ.A.	84	
NAVY	Ö.A.	80	
Infantry	A.V.D.	91	
GENERAL (**)	A.N.E.	81	Two-Star-General
Ordnance	Ö.R.M.	88	
Engineering Corps (Fortifications)	M.K.	81	
STAFF (of Artillery)	K.R.G.	82	
Personnel Officer	N.Ü.	77	
NAVAL Engineer	M.D.	80	Record: 1952-38
Personnel Officer	N.K.	77	
Air Force Pilot	F.G.	86	
Signals	F.B.	86	
Artillery	A.Y.	70	
STAFF (of Tank)	O.G.	80	
Personnel Officer	N.K.	88	
Quartermaster	M.M.Ö.	77	
Air Force Ground Officer	G.A.	84	
Infantry	R.U.	80	
Artillery	A.O.Y.	87	
Infantry	Y.O.	71	

END of the 2nd Journal. Out of 68 obituary notices five were honorary civilian members; 17 were officers' wives. Net number of entries is 46.

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81.9 is the average of this table.

The 3rd Journal: Issue Number 172, November-December 2007

Officer's Branch	Initials (Name)	Age at Death	Explanations if Required (Crushing majority are colonels, some have lower ranks like LT-Col or Major)
Personnel Officer	S.Ö.	84	
Air Force Signals	A.N.E.	88	
Infantry	M.F.Ö.	82	
Infantry	H.R.A.	86	
Gendarme	Ö.G.	85	
Tank	E.S.	76	
Air Force Ground Officer	R.Ü.	86	
Air Force Ground Officer	O.K.	86	
Engineer	S.A.T.	70	Record: 1957-196
NAVY-Supples	M.K.	83	
Infantry	A.C.	66	
Infantry	R.S.	92	
Transportation	M.R.A.	81	
Tank	M.S.M.	87	
Air Force-Signals	N.A.	73	
Air Force-Master Mechanical Engineer	D.S.E.	81	(5 years of higher schooling) (at the time M.S. degrees were granted in 5 years by skipping the B.S.)
Infantry	A.Ç.	74	
Air Force-Engineering Corps (Fortifications)	T.T.	68	
Veterinary Surgeon	M.S.	90	Record: 1940-6 (5 years of higher schooling)
Personnel Officer (of Gendarmerie)	L.Ç.	61	
Air Force-Signals	E.G.B.	85	
Air Force-Intelligence	Y.E.	68	The Branch of Intelligence was instigated in late 1990s (transferred from other combat branches).
Infantry	H.R.Y.	88	
Air Force-Pilot	A.H.G.	80	
Quartermaster	K.Ç.	73	
Personnel Officer	K.Ş.	72	
Gendarme	M.Z.H.	85	
Infantry	V.Ç.	60	
Personnel Officer	G.V.A.	73	
Infantry	K.Ş.	84	
Gendarme	C.S.	85	
Veterinary Surgeon	M.K.H.	84	Record: 1940-6 (5 years of higher schooling)
Quartermaster	D.Ö.	86	
Artillery	G.G.	58	
Gendarme	H.A.	84	
Infantry	T.A.	84	

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Infantry	K.K.	81	
Air Force - GENERAL (*)	H.Ş.Y.	79	Two-Star- General of Air Force
Artillery	E.P.	76	
Topographical Engineer	O.B.	67	Topographical Engineers are transferred from combat officers. (They attend further courses, not a university).
END of the 3rd Journal. Out of 50 obituary notices two were civilians, who were sons of officers; 8 were officers' wives. Net number of entries is 40. 79.0 is the average of this table.			
The 4th Journal: Issue Number 196, April-May-June 2012			
Officer's Branch	Initials (Name)	Age at Death	Explanations if Required (Crushing majority are colonels, some have lower ranks like LT-Col or Major)
Artillery	E.C.M.	80	
Infantry	S.E.	81	
Artillery	T.Ç.	75	
Infantry	S.F.T.	88	
Tank	H.M.	84	
	A.V.H.	90	Colonel from Şişli. Branch unidentified.
Quartermaster	K.Y.	81	
Transportation	İ.T.	85	
Quartermaster	H.A.O.	91	
Artillery	M.I.D.	90	
Infantry	H.D.	93	
Veterinary Surgeon	T.T.	93	Record: 1944-16 (5 years of higher schooling)
Personnel Officer	M.B.	77	
GENERAL (**)	R.K.	83	Two-Star-General
GENERAL (**)	T.T.	82	Two-Star-General
	M.A.E.	58	Colonel from Kadıköy. Branch unidentified.
Infantry	A.S.T.	87	
	S.T.	88	Colonel from Şişli. Branch unidentified.
Quartermaster	S.U.	83	
Tank	M.O.S.	87	
Infantry	B.U.	71	
Artillery	M.E.Y	83	
Veterinary Surgeon	H.A.A.	93	Record: 1942-2 (5 years of higher schooling)
Artillery	K.K.	85	
Medical Doctor	M.Ö.	93	Record: 1953-38 (6 years of higher schooling)
	M.K.Ç.	82	Colonel from Şişli. Branch unidentified.
Artillery	T.İ.	81	
Artillery	T.Y.	85	
Infantry	F.L.	81	
Artillery	M.K.E.	85	
	S.A.	80	Colonel from Bakırköy. Branch unidentified.
Military School Teacher	Y.K.	74	Record: 1960-4 (4 years of higher schooling)
Infantry	A.G.	92	

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	N.U.	83	Colonel from Bakırköy. Branch unidentified.
Air Force- Ground Officer	U.B.	84	
GENERAL (*)	M.Ç.	63	One-Star-General
Infantry	I.U.	63	
END of the 4th Journal. Out of 48 obituary notices two were honorary civilian members; 9 were officers' wives. Net number of entries is 37. 82.7 is the average of this table.			
The 5th Journal: Issue No.194, October-November-December 2011			
Officer's Branch	Initials (Name)	Age at Death	Explanations if Required (Crushing majority are colonels, some have lower ranks like LT-Col or Major)
Signals	R.A.	79	
Gendarme	A.N.S.	81	
Medical Doctor	Ş.Ü.	93	(6 years of higher schooling)
Gendarme	S.Z.G.	90	
Air Force- Ground Officer	E.T.	83	
Infantry	C.I.	82	
Artillery	S.F.A.	83	
Artillery	İ.F.Ü.	83	
Infantry	H.Ö.	87	
Air Force- Ground Officer	İ.Y.	64	
	M.M.Ö.	83	Colonel from Konak. Branch unidentified.
Air Force- Ground Officer	E.Z.	72	
	T.S.		Colonel from Antalya. Branch unidentified. Record Number and accordingly age is also unidentified.
Air Force- Ground Officer	A.G.		Colonel from Çankaya. Record Number and accordingly age is also unidentified.
Air Force- Ground Officer	F.İ.	82	
Transportation	N.G.	75	
Gendarme	S.S.	70	
NAVY	S.D.	75	
Artillery	A.M.Y.	74	
Infantry	Ö.B.	70	
	C.G.	52	Major from Çorlu. Branch unidentified. 1981 graduate: Four years of higher schooling.
Transportation	M.A.	85	
	N.O.		Record Number and accordingly age is also unidentified.
Transportation	A.N.B.	84	
STAFF (of Artillery)	E.T.	91	
Infantry	C.A.	90	
Personnel Officer	Z.U.	75	

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Signals	N.I.	84	
Personnel Officer	M.M.	76	
STAFF (of Artillery	H.C.	90	
Tank	M.H.A.	86	
Military Pharmacist	I.D.	93	Record: 1940-124. Rank is senior captain, which could only mean retired due to disability. (4 years of higher schooling)
Medical Doctor	I.E.G.	82	Record: 1953-9 (6years of higher schooling)
GENERAL (*)	I.H.T.	90	One-Strar-General
Infantry	N.T.A.	80	
Signals	N.D.		Lt-Col. From Antalya. Record Number and accordingly age is also unidentified.
Infantry	T.F.Y.		The Record is meaningless:129-54 A Print-Mistake. Thereby, age unidentified.
Medical Doctor	H.C.U.	74	Record: 1961:253 (6 years of higher schooling)
Infantry	M.K.	82	
Air Force- Ground Officer	A.T.O.	83	
Quartermaster	Ö.Y.	77	
Air Force-Infantry	M.H.B.	78	
Personnel Officer	H.Y.	76	
Air Force-Military Teacher	I.G.	55	Record: 1983-2. FEMALE OFFICER. Civilian Uni. Graduate. Age Below 30 in Commission. (Admission procedure takes a few years). Approximate guess: 53 >Age >58 55 is accepted.
Artillery	A.R.Z.	92	
Ordnance	Z.K.	78	
Air Force- Ground Officer	Y.Z.Y.	81	Record: 1950-58. Rank is senior captain, which could only mean retired due to disability.
Personnel Officer	S.A.	90	
Engineer	H.T.	66	(4 years of higher schooling)
Tank	K.G.	63	
Quartermaster	F.G.	90	
Signals	S.N.Y.	90	
Air Force- Ground Officer	A.R.E.	90	
NAVY Lieutenant-retiree.	E.S.	29	NAVY RECORD: 1995-7496. From Lüleburgaz. Prep School & 4 years of higher schooling taken into account in age-determining. Obviously disability retirement. THE SHORTEST LIFE SPAN. The rank is very small and not representative, though.
GENERAL (***)	C.I.	76	Three-Star-General
Artillery	Ş.T.	80	
Signals	M.S.A.	92	Husband of the first female officer.
END of the 5th Journal. Out of 56 obituary notices three were honorary civilian members; 6were officers' wives. Net number of entries is 47.			

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81.2 is the average of this table.

The 6th Journal: Issue No. 193, July-August-September 2011

Officer's Branch	Initials (Name)	Age at Death	Explanations if Required (Crushing majority are colonels, some have lower ranks like LT-Col or Major)
Signals	M.Ç.	94	
Artillery	İ.E.S.	73	
Personnel Officer	N.K.E.	77	
Personnel Officer	M.M.	75	
STAFF Officer	H.D.	92	
Artillery	H.T.	93	
NAVY	M.N.T.	92	
Quartermaster	N.S.	75	
Finance officer	K.K.	77	
Infantry	Y.K.	78	
NAVY	A.B.	84	
STAFF Officer	A.T.	90	
Medical Doctor	H.B.	79	Record: 1956-44 (6 years of higher schooling)
Infantry	Ş.E.G.	63	
STAFF Officer	S.K.A.	94	
Gendarme	S.B.S.	82	
Master Engineer	İ.E.B.	93	Record: 1941-1 (5 years of higher schooling) (at the time M.S. degrees were granted in 5 years by skipping the B.S.)
Personnel Officer	K.Ö.	86	
NAVY	L.O.	84	
Quartermaster	H.K.K.	89	
Infantry	N.K.	77	
NAVY	N.D.	77	
Engineering corps	C.O.	57	Record: 1975-1 (3 years of higher schooling)
Artillery	F.Ü.	87	
Quartermaster	R.T.	86	
Gendarme	İ.A.	84	
Air Force Pilot	H.F.D.	82	
Personnel Officer	H.B.	82	
Engineering corps	H.M.S.	90	
Ground Force Pilot	M.O.	78	
Artillery	H.A.	80	
Personnel Officer	C.G.	88	

END of the 6th Journal. Out of 49 obituary notices three were honorary civilian members; 2 were female honorary members; 8 were officers' wives; 1 was an officer's daughter; 1 was an officer's son. Net number of entries is 34.

82.3 is the average of this table.

The 7th Journal: Issue No. 198, October-November-December 2012

Officer's Branch	Initials	Age at	Explanations if Required
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	(Name	Death	(Crushing majority are colonels, some have lower ranks like LT-Col or Major)
NAVY	A.Ö.	72	
Air Force Pilot	O.İ.	70	
	A.T.D.	85	Colonel from Bakırköy. Branch unidentified.
Infantry	Ç.S.	64	
Artillery	F.K.	91	
Artillery	A.G.	77	
Military Judge	N.K.	83	Record: 1953-1 (4 years of higher schooling)
Air Force-Ground Officer	S.N.K.	85	
Infantry	M.B.	85	
Air Force-Pilot	E.K.	74	
GENERAL (**)	M.C.B.	85	Two-Star-General
Infantry	S.Ç.	96	
Military Judge	K.C.	84	Record: 1950-3 (4 years of higher schooling)
Infantry	N.A.	97	
Veterinary Surgeon	B.B.	74	Record: 1961-7 (5 years of higher schooling)
Infantry	A.E.	94	
Infantry	N.Y.	77	
GENERAL (*)	M.E.	81	One-Star-General
NAVY	S.P.	91	
Quartermaster	M.N.U.	89	
Artillery	M.O.	68	
Artillery	T.Ö.	91	
(Air Force) Military Teacher	Öner Can	72	Record: 1962-5 (4 years of higher schooling) THE RESEARCHER KNEW HIM FROM HIS OWN SERVICE DAYS. (MAY GOD-ALMIGHTY BLESS THE COLONEL'S SOUL!)
Personnel Officer	H.R.R.	76	
Tank	N.K.	78	
Air Force- Transportation	Z.G.	78	
Personnel Officer	A.K.	77	
Tank	G.A.	85	
Military Teacher	R.H.E.	83	(4 years of higher schooling)
Personnel Officer	A.F.S.	85	
NAVAL Engineer	M.K.	80	NAVY Record: 1952-2308
Medical Doctor	E.Ş.A.	85	Record:1951-29 (6 years of higher schooling)
Air Force-Ground Officer	H.B.	83	
Tank	S.Y.E.	74	
Infantry	K.N.E.	84	
Artillery	G.S.	68	
Air Force-Ground Officer	A.F.A.	77	
Personnel Officer	A.G.	71	
Artillery	C.L.	78	
Gendarme	Ş.Y.	94	

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Quartermaster	H.N.S.	91	
Gendarme	A.H.E.	91	
Gendarme	S.N.E.	85	
GENERAL (**)	E.S.G.	75	Two-Star-General
END of the 7th Journal. Out of 58 obituary notices 1 was an honorary civilian member; 1 was a female honorary member; 10 were officers' wives; 2 were officers' daughter. Net number of entries is 44. 81.4 is the average of this table.			
The 8th Journal: Issue No. 173, January-February 2008			
Officer's Branch	Initials (Name)	Age at Death	Explanations if Required (Crushing majority are colonels, some have lower ranks like LT-Col or Major)
Infantry	S.B.	87	
Military Teacher	E.I.	67	
NAVAL STAFF Officer	H.T.K.	79	
Signals	A.S.Ü.	91	
Air Force-Ground Officer	R.Y.	71	
Ordnance	M.K.	65	
Air Force-Ground Officer	Y.K.	87	
NAVAL Judge	C.A.	75	
GENERAL (***)	K.T.	93	Three-Star-General
Engineering corps	Ş.K.	84	
Signals	Ö.A.	70	
Transportation	Ö.S.	79	
NAVAL Medical Doctor	A.İ.D.	55	Record: 1973-1
Air Force-Medical Doctor	Ö.S.S.	79	Record: 1952-16 (6 years of higher schooling)
Infantry	F.A.	88	
STAFF (of Artillery)	M.H.İ.	95	
STAFF (of Artillery)	S.E.	85	
Ordnance	İ.K.	86	
Medical Doctor	N.E.	78	Record: 1953-49 (6 years of higher schooling)
Air Force-Personnel Officer	S.D.T.	84	
Air Force Pilot GENERAL (*)	M.T.A.	56	
Air Force-Ground Officer	A.T.	80	
Air Force-Signals	E.T.	78	
Personnel Officer	C.Ö.	81	
	Z.B.	86	Colonel from Şişli. Branch unidentified.
Gendarme	M.N.K.	76	
Infantry	M.S.D.	93	
Quartermaster	H.S.	87	
Artillery	M.S.	85	
Medical doctor	İ.G.	61	Record: 1971-121 (6 years of higher schooling)

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Engineering corps	B.Ö.	80	
Quartermaster	O.S.	72	
Artillery	S.T.	85	
Quartermaster	N.A.	87	
Signals	N.A.	75	
Quartermaster	Z.G.	65	
Personel Officer	M.G.	86	Record: 1941-P-239 (Transfer from P / infantry) (Branch should be personel.Since both words start with "P" there is a mistake. He is eventually personel, not P/ infantry.
Infantry	K.S.	85	
Ordnance	S.S.	79	
Infantry	N.O.	84	
Quartermaster	H.A.	91	
Military Teacher	S.T.	88	(4 years of higher schooling)
Infantry	M.S.	71	A captain-retiree. Must be due to disability.
Tank	H.V.T.	85	
Quartermaster	N.Ç.	86	
Air Force- Engineering corps	G.Ç.	71	
Personnel Officer	Y.A.	95	
Quartermaster	A.G.	79	
Personnel Officer	E.G.	69	
Artillery	O.Ç.	62	
Infantry	H.C.Ö.	88	It is specified that he is a resignee from the rank of captain.

END of the 8th Journal. Out of 60 obituary notices 6 were officers' wives; 1 was an officer's daughter. Net number of entries is 53.

79.6 is the average of this table.

The 9th Journal: Issue No. 200, April-May-June 2013

Officer's Branch	Initials (Name)	Age at Death	Explanations if Required (Crushing majority are colonels, some have lower ranks like LT-Col or Major)
Air Force-Ground officer	M.H.B.	84	
Air Force -Staff officer	M.Ö.	83	
Air Force-Ground officer	T.G.		Senior Air Force Colonel from Antalya. Record Number and accordingly age is also unidentified.
Air Force-Ground officer	A.M.A.	90	
Personnel Officer	Y.M.E.	77	
Artillery	İ.E.	85	
Infantry	N.E.	87	
Ordnance	T.Y.	85	
Ordnance	H.B.	72	
Military Teacher	N.E.	89	(4 years of higher schooling)
GENERAL (***)	M.F.O.	86	Three-Star-General
Artillery	N.A.E.	78	

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Personnel Officer	K.K.	79	
Tank	İ.İ.	67	
NAVAL STAFF Officer	M.İ.E.	64	
Military Teacher	S.E.	72	
Air Force-engineer	D.K.	77	Partial Record given as “1958”. The Colonel was from Çankaya. (4 years of higher schooling)
GENERAL (**)	M.K.K.	88	Two-Star-General
Infantry	R.S.	87	
NAVY	M.K.	85	
	H.S.	77	Branch not specified. Retiree-captain so he must be a disabled-retiree.
Infantry	O.C.	76	
Infantry	M.D.	83	
Personel Officer	A.B.	92	
Tank	İ.G.K.	81	
Quartermaster	A.A.	78	
Infantry	B.S.	77	
Engineering corps	Ş.Ö.	82	
Artillery	T.D.	76	
STAFF Officer	A.E.	77	
Infantry	S.Z.Ş.	80	
GENERAL (*)	T.N.		One-Star-General from Râsimpaşa. Record not specified and accordingly age unot determined.
Air Force Ground Officer	A.Ö.	90	
	S.Z.K.	84	The Senior Major is from Bolu Section of the Retirees’ Association. A page is devoted to him. But his military branch is not specified.
<p>END of the 9th Journal. Out of 45 obituary notices 9 were officers’ wives; 1 was an honorary civilian member; 1 was an honorary female member. Net number of entries is 34.</p> <p>81.0 is the average of this table.</p>			
<p>The 10th(Last) Journal: Issue No. 190, November-December 2010</p>			
Officer’s Branch	Initials (Name)	Age at Death	Explanations if Required (Crushing majority are colonels, some have lower ranks like LT-Col or Major)
Ordnance	M.F.İ.		Record not given; accordingly age not determined.
Infantry	H.F.S.	94	
Infantry Colonel	Feridun Doralp	99	Military Record: 1931-26. From Çankaya. The longest LIFE SPAN encountered in this research!
STAFF (of Infantry)	A.E.	84	

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Artillery	O.N.T.	77	
STAFF (of Artillery)	N.T.O.	83	
Quartermaster	A.Y.Y.	77	
Tank	A.S.	92	
Air Force-Ground officer	G.E.	64	
Personel Officer	A.F.T.	75	
Personel Officer	H.H.Ö.	79	
Personel Officer	S.E.	87	
Quartermaster of GENDARMERIE	F.N.	75	
Air Force GENERAL (*)	K.E.	74	One-Star-General of the Air Force
Air Force GENERAL (*)	İ.B.	90	One-Star-General of the Air Force
Engineering corps	S.K.	87	
Infantry	R.M.S.	70	
Infantry Major	S.A.	49	Record:1972-78. Three years of higher schooling (nearer times) taken into account in age-determining. The second shortest life span, again from Lüleburgaz.
Jet-Maintenance- STAFF Officer	K.Ş.A.	74	A Staff Officer from an auxiliary branch! (Most STAFF officers come from pilots in the air Force).
NAVAL Military Teacher	H.D.E.	91	(4 years of higher schooling)
Infantry	A.M.Ö.	74	
Tank	S.T.	64	
Signals	F.D.	70	
Personel Officer	E.E.	75	
NAVY	C.P.	79	
NAVAL Military Teacher	T.K.	68	
Signals	H.D.	81	
Personel Officer	R.A.	74	
Military Teacher	A.T.Y.	77	(4 years of higher schooling)
Infantry	A.A.	89	
GENDARME	M.R.E.	83	
GENERAL (*) of Ordnance Branch	F.Ç.	87	Crushing majority of generals are promoted from STAFF officers. This is a sheer exception!
Infantry	E.P.	65	
END of the 10th (Last) Journal. Out of 42 obituary notices 5 were officers' wives; 1 was an honorary civilian member.Net number of entries is 36. 77.8 is the average of this table.			
Total Average: 81.1			

EXPLANATION

The War College after lycée (high school) used to be a 2-year-long junior college; and this is the basis of calculations for combat as well as combat-support officers. Those with sheer university degrees (medical doctors, veterinery surgeons, teachers of academic fields, engineers) had longer

higher education; and computations were made accordingly. {Let us note that an *engineer* is a B.S.-degree-holder from a university, while a member of the *engineering corps* (reinforcer of defence-lines) is a War College graduate}.

THE JOURNALS EMPLOYED IN THIS STUDY

CODE: ZABİT 01 (Issue Number 197, July-August-September 2012) [Ref. No. 6]

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ARAMIZDAN AYRILANLAR

Kederli ailelerine ve arkadaşlarına başsağlığı diler, huzurlu istirahatte olmalarını dileriz.

TESU'D Genel Merkezi

YAB ERMAN Em. İst. E.İ. A.B. (1953-12) Karakaya Şh. Eysel Vat. Tar. 23.047.2812 Adres: Karakaya Cad. No:13 D:20 Karakaya-İSTANBUL Tel: (0212) 283 74 82	Haluk SOYLU Sulay E.İ. Karakaya Şh. Eysel Vat. Tar. 23.047.2812 Adres: Karakaya Cad. No:13 D:20 Karakaya-İSTANBUL Tel: (0212) 283 74 82	Nezir SÖNMEZ Em. İst. E.İ. A.B. (1953-12) Karakaya Şh. Eysel Vat. Tar. 23.047.2812 Adres: Karakaya Cad. No:13 D:20 Karakaya-İSTANBUL Tel: (0212) 283 74 82	Haluk SOYLU Sulay E.İ. Karakaya Şh. Eysel Vat. Tar. 23.047.2812 Adres: Karakaya Cad. No:13 D:20 Karakaya-İSTANBUL Tel: (0212) 283 74 82	Mustafa NERLAN Em. İst. E.İ. A.B. (1947-13) Karakaya Şh. Eysel Vat. Tar. 23.047.2812 Adres: Karakaya Cad. No:13 D:20 Karakaya-İSTANBUL Tel: (0212) 283 74 82	Mustafa NERLAN Em. İst. E.İ. A.B. (1947-13) Karakaya Şh. Eysel Vat. Tar. 23.047.2812 Adres: Karakaya Cad. No:13 D:20 Karakaya-İSTANBUL Tel: (0212) 283 74 82
Nezir SÖNMEZ Em. İst. E.İ. A.B. (1953-12) Karakaya Şh. Eysel Vat. Tar. 23.047.2812 Adres: Karakaya Cad. No:13 D:20 Karakaya-İSTANBUL Tel: (0212) 283 74 82	Haluk SOYLU Sulay E.İ. Karakaya Şh. Eysel Vat. Tar. 23.047.2812 Adres: Karakaya Cad. No:13 D:20 Karakaya-İSTANBUL Tel: (0212) 283 74 82	Mustafa NERLAN Em. İst. E.İ. A.B. (1947-13) Karakaya Şh. Eysel Vat. Tar. 23.047.2812 Adres: Karakaya Cad. No:13 D:20 Karakaya-İSTANBUL Tel: (0212) 283 74 82	Mustafa NERLAN Em. İst. E.İ. A.B. (1947-13) Karakaya Şh. Eysel Vat. Tar. 23.047.2812 Adres: Karakaya Cad. No:13 D:20 Karakaya-İSTANBUL Tel: (0212) 283 74 82	Mustafa NERLAN Em. İst. E.İ. A.B. (1947-13) Karakaya Şh. Eysel Vat. Tar. 23.047.2812 Adres: Karakaya Cad. No:13 D:20 Karakaya-İSTANBUL Tel: (0212) 283 74 82	Mustafa NERLAN Em. İst. E.İ. A.B. (1947-13) Karakaya Şh. Eysel Vat. Tar. 23.047.2812 Adres: Karakaya Cad. No:13 D:20 Karakaya-İSTANBUL Tel: (0212) 283 74 82

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Emrah KARALANAN Em. İst. E.İ. A.B. (1953-12) Karakaya Şh. Eysel Vat. Tar. 23.047.2812 Adres: Karakaya Cad. No:13 D:20 Karakaya-İSTANBUL Tel: (0212) 283 74 82	Mehmet ER Em. İst. E.İ. A.B. (1953-12) Karakaya Şh. Eysel Vat. Tar. 23.047.2812 Adres: Karakaya Cad. No:13 D:20 Karakaya-İSTANBUL Tel: (0212) 283 74 82	Mehmet ER Em. İst. E.İ. A.B. (1953-12) Karakaya Şh. Eysel Vat. Tar. 23.047.2812 Adres: Karakaya Cad. No:13 D:20 Karakaya-İSTANBUL Tel: (0212) 283 74 82	Mehmet ER Em. İst. E.İ. A.B. (1953-12) Karakaya Şh. Eysel Vat. Tar. 23.047.2812 Adres: Karakaya Cad. No:13 D:20 Karakaya-İSTANBUL Tel: (0212) 283 74 82	Mehmet ER Em. İst. E.İ. A.B. (1953-12) Karakaya Şh. Eysel Vat. Tar. 23.047.2812 Adres: Karakaya Cad. No:13 D:20 Karakaya-İSTANBUL Tel: (0212) 283 74 82	Mehmet ER Em. İst. E.İ. A.B. (1953-12) Karakaya Şh. Eysel Vat. Tar. 23.047.2812 Adres: Karakaya Cad. No:13 D:20 Karakaya-İSTANBUL Tel: (0212) 283 74 82

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<p>Bülent Sözü ERGÜNÖRSÖZ Etn. Türk. K.A. Ad. (1941-40) Başşehir Şh. Eyalet Yıldız Tesisleri 28/10/2012 Adres: Yedigöller Sok. No:3977 New Apt. Beşiktaş Kadıköy-İSTANBUL Tel: (0216) 340 47 13</p>	<p>M. Ali CAN Etn. Türk. K.A. Ad. (1952-32) Başşehir Şh. Eyalet Yıldız Tesisleri 28/10/2012 Adres: Etiler Katmanlı Mah. Çiğdem Sok. No:52 BAŞŞEHİR Tel: (0216) 429 11 88</p>	<p>M. Ömer BİNGÖZ Etn. Türk. K.A. Ad. (1953-110) Kadıköy Şh. Eyalet Yıldız Tesisleri 28/10/2012 Adres: Yedigöller Çk. Zeki Fırat Sok. No:1918 Etiler D/22 Kadıköy-İSTANBUL Tel: (0216) 361 66 60</p>	<p>Hüsnü BOYLUCUOĞLU Etn. Türk. K.A. Ad. (1951-51) Kadıköy Şh. Eyalet Yıldız Tesisleri 28/10/2012 Adres: Etiler Çalgı Cad. Etiler Sok. No:117 GÜP-ANKARA Tel: (0212) 417 22 08</p>
<p>Abdül Nispet ÇITAK Etn. Türk. K.A. Ad. (1942-38) Başşehir Şh. Eyalet Yıldız Tesisleri 28/10/2012 Adres: Başkent Cad. Fenerbahçe Sk. No:131-206 Katmanlı Mah. Beşiktaş-İSTANBUL Tel: (0216) 340 47 13</p>	<p>M. Ömer ÖZATA Etn. Türk. K.A. Ad. (1943-30) Kadıköy Şh. Eyalet Yıldız Tesisleri 28/10/2012 Adres: 1701 Sok. No:473 Kadıköy-İSTANBUL Tel: (0212) 361 66 19</p>	<p>M. Ömer BİNGÖZ Etn. Türk. K.A. Ad. (1953-110) Kadıköy Şh. Eyalet Yıldız Tesisleri 28/10/2012 Adres: Yedigöller Apt. Sok. No:1918 Etiler D/22 Kadıköy-İSTANBUL Tel: (0216) 403 72 04</p>	<p>Yasin TENİZ Etn. Türk. K.A. Ad. (1943-13) Başşehir Şh. Eyalet Yıldız Tesisleri 28/10/2012 Adres: Döner Köprüler Mah. Dr. Şahin Altınsoy Cad. No:449 Beşiktaş-İSTANBUL Tel: (0212) 451 83 18</p>
<p>Filiz YETİNCİOĞLU Etn. Türk. K.A. Ad. (1942-45) Kadıköy Şh. Eyalet Yıldız Tesisleri 28/10/2012 Adres: Çiğdemli Çarşı Dr. Sok. No:1918 Kadıköy-İSTANBUL Tel: (0216) 330 69 67</p>	<p>Fahriye ÖZANCI Etn. Türk. K.A. Ad. (1941-3) Kadıköy Şh. Eyalet Yıldız Tesisleri 28/10/2012 Adres: 1701 Sok. No: 473 D/8 Kadıköy-İSTANBUL Tel: (0212) 361 24 96</p>	<p>Mehmet İBRAHİM Etn. Türk. K.A. Ad. (1951-7) Kadıköy Şh. Eyalet Yıldız Tesisleri 28/10/2012 Adres: 561 Sıca Sok. Beşiktaş Etiler Apt. D:25 Başşehir-İSTANBUL Tel: (0212) 266 17 68</p>	<p>H. Mehmet ÖZMEZ Etn. Türk. K.A. Ad. (1942-48) Kadıköy Şh. Eyalet Yıldız Tesisleri 28/10/2012 Adres: Çiğdemli Köprüsü Sok. Etiler Apt. No:1372 Kadıköy-İSTANBUL Tel: (0216) 417 30 39</p>
<p>Sahabe ÖZDEMİR Şahin Etiler Kadıköy Şh. Eyalet Yıldız Tesisleri 28/10/2012 Adres: Yedigöller Sok. No:3977 New Apt. Beşiktaş-ANKARA Tel: (0212) 266 17 68</p>	<p>İ. Seda PEŞİNTÜRK Etn. Türk. K.A. Ad. (1945-19) Kadıköy Şh. Eyalet Yıldız Tesisleri 28/10/2012 Adres: Beşiktaş Mah. 497 Sok. No:200 Sok. B. Blok D:18 Çiğdemli-ANKARA Tel: (0212) 496 15 85</p>	<p>Çiğdem EDİCİ Etn. Türk. K.A. Ad. (1958-38) Kadıköy Şh. Eyalet Yıldız Tesisleri 28/10/2012 Adres: Yedigöller Mah. Beşiktaş-ANKARA Tel: (0212) 266 17 68</p>	<p>Bülent ADAZ Etn. Türk. K.A. Ad. (1968-48) Kadıköy Şh. Eyalet Yıldız Tesisleri 28/10/2012 Adres: Çiğdemli Köprüsü Sok. Etiler Sok. Kat. Apt. No:108 Çiğdemli-İSTANBUL Tel: (0216) 340 28 74</p>
<p>Ali DEMİR Etn. Türk. K.A. Ad. (1946-79) Kadıköy Şh. Eyalet Yıldız Tesisleri 28/10/2012 Adres: Mevlana Bulvarı Cad. No:1913 Saray-İSTANBUL Tel: (0212) 266 17 68</p>	<p>Nesrin ÖZGEN Şahin Etiler Kadıköy Şh. Eyalet Yıldız Tesisleri 28/10/2012 Adres: Uğur Mustafa Cad. Uğur Mustafa Sok. No:51 GÜP-ANKARA Tel: (0212) 427 68 18</p>	<p>Abdullah ERGÜN Çiğdemli (Etiler) Etiler Kadıköy Şh. Eyalet Yıldız Tesisleri 28/10/2012 Adres: Çiğdemli Mah. Beşiktaş-ANKARA No:1913 Saray-İSTANBUL Tel: (0212) 266 17 68</p>	<p>Yasin ÖZCAN Etn. Türk. K.A. Ad. (1947-33) Başşehir Şh. Eyalet Yıldız Tesisleri 28/10/2012 Adres: Zeytinli Mah. Beşiktaş-ANKARA No:1913 Saray-İSTANBUL Tel: (0212) 266 17 68</p>

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<p>Hakkı BEYKARACI Em. DİN. K.İ.Ş. AB. (1954-46) Konya Şh. Eysel Vize Tarihi: 13/06/2011 E-Adresi: Yab. Cad. No:206-2 Konya-İZMİR Tel: 033232 301 31 46</p>	<p>A. Errol DEĞİRCİ İzmir Üni. Çankaya Şh. Eysel Vize Tarihi: 09/06/2011 E-Adresi: Kalkınımçılar Mah. 219 Sok. Kızılkaya Apt. No:313 GÜLŞAN-KARŞI Tel: 0312) 495 74 51</p>	<p>L.ÖRÜ ÖZAN SALTI. GÜN. K.İ. AB. (1947-2011) Marmara Şh. Eysel Vize Tarihi: 04/07/2011 E-Adresi: Söğütler Mah. 212 Sok. ÖZEL APT. NO:97 MEYDANBAZI Tel: 0312) 365 90 67</p>	<p>Hüseyin Kemal KOÇKARAYA Em. İ.Ş. K.İ. AB. (1944-49) Konya Şh. Eysel Vize Tarihi: 04/07/2011 E-Adresi: Şehitlik Yolu. 21inci Apt. No:211 Kadim-İSTANBUL Tel: 0312) 353 90 67</p>
<p>Zahide SAYMAN Sakarya Şh. Eysel Konya Şh. Eysel Vize Tarihi: 20/06/2011 E-Adresi: Mevlâni Bulvarı Balıka Sok. Palas Apt. No:109 Konya-İSTANBUL Tel: 0312) 337 44 36</p>	<p>Ömer DEMİRCİOĞLU Em. P. K.İ. AB. (1934-2011) Konya Şh. Eysel Vize Tarihi: 22/06/2011 E-Adresi: Emekliye Kayıt Aof Tolunca Sok. No: 259 KARŞI-İSTANBUL Tel: 0312) 467 99 83</p>	<p>Neval KİPÇELİ Em. F.İ.Ş. AB. (1954-19) Konya Şh. Eysel Vize Tarihi: 14/07/2011 E-Adresi: Dışişleri Cad. Nispetiye Binası 52/208 Tel: 0312) 347 65 50</p>	<p>Şehinşah BALARAN Konya Şh. Eysel Konya Şh. Eysel Vize Tarihi: 14/07/2011 E-Adresi: Çarşıbaşı İstasyon Yolu Caddesi Apt. No:207 Konya-İSTANBUL Tel: 0312) 353 26 32</p>
<p>Sabah Endemir ÇENİCİ Em. İ.Ş. (1968-2011) Konya Şh. Eysel Vize Tarihi: 20/06/2011 E-Adresi: Hasan Etiler Sok. No:1172 Şişli- İSTANBUL Tel: 0312) 369 98 31</p>	<p>Sahit Kıvanç ARKIN Em. K.İ. AB. (1977-14) Konya Şh. Eysel Vize Tarihi: 29/06/2011 E-Adresi: Ömer Çelebi Cad. Kıvanç Sok. No:27 D.6 Konya-İSTANBUL Tel: 0312) 361 89 82</p>	<p>Yusuf PAFTUCCİ Fahri Üye Konya Şh. Eysel Vize Tarihi: 09/07/2011 E-Adresi: İstasyon Cad. No:749 54 Piyalepağ-İZMİR Tel: 0312) 229 36 13</p>	<p>Sevcan KUTMAN Fahri Üye Konya Şh. Eysel Vize Tarihi: 22/07/2011 E-Adresi: Nispetiye Cad. Pınar Sok. No:121 Şişli-İSTANBUL Tel: 0312) 352 38 84</p>
<p>Sabah BAŞARAN Sakarya Şh. Eysel Konya Şh. Eysel Vize Tarihi: 09/07/2011 E-Adresi: Emekli Sok. 83 Blok D.3 Beşiktaş-İSTANBUL Tel: 0312) 369 98 31</p>	<p>Sahit Berhan SARI Em. İ.Ş. K.İ. AB. (1940-52) Çankaya Şh. Eysel Vize Tarihi: 09/07/2011 E-Adresi: An Sok. Kızı Apt. No:20 Konya-İSTANBUL Tel: 0312) 229 23 99</p>	<p>Adnan ÇÖLLEKÇİ Em. İ.Ş. K.İ. AB. (1954-2011) Konya Şh. Eysel Vize Tarihi: 28/07/2011 E-Adresi: Şahinbey Emekli Aof Papa Cad. Tunalıbaşı Sok. Kızı Apt. No:568 Konya-İSTANBUL Tel: 0312) 464 11 72</p>	<p>Nihat DAYI Em. İ.Ş. K.İ. AB. (1954-2011) Konya Şh. Eysel Vize Tarihi: 28/07/2011 E-Adresi: Tunalıbaşı Sok. Halıbaşı Cad. No:121 Şişli-İSTANBUL Konya-İSTANBUL Tel: 0312) 353 26 32</p>
<p>İbrahim Etiler BARLAS Em. İ.Ş. K.İ. AB. (1941-11) Konya Şh. Eysel Vize Tarihi: 06/07/2011 E-Adresi: Çarşı Emekli Cad. No:422 19 12 Konya-İZMİR Tel: 0312) 361 29 69</p>	<p>Kemal ÖZDOĞAN Em. İ.Ş. K.İ. AB. (1940-52) Çankaya Şh. Eysel Vize Tarihi: 09/07/2011 E-Adresi: Emekli Sok. 27 No:1 Sok. No:21 Çankaya-ANKARA Tel: 0312) 318 62 22</p>	<p>Çevdet ÖZAL Em. İ.Ş. (1975-11) Konya Şh. Eysel Vize Tarihi: 26/07/2011 E-Adresi: Kızılkaya Mah. Çelebi Sok. No:155 Beşiktaş-İSTANBUL Tel: 0312) 229 36 13</p>	<p>Fikret ÇİFTÇİ Em. İ.Ş. K.İ. AB. (1944-54) Konya Şh. Eysel Vize Tarihi: 08/08/2011 E-Adresi: Çarşı Sok. İstasyon Cad. Hürriyet Sok. A Blok No:72/4 Beşiktaş-İSTANBUL Tel: 0312) 361 89 79</p>

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<p>Kemal F. ERKAR Em. İ.Ş. K.İ. AB. (1945-54) Çankaya Şh. Eysel Vize Tarihi: 04/08/2011 E-Adresi: Ankara Cad. Dersin Apt. No:918 Beşiktaş-ANKARA Tel: 0312) 222 36 79</p>	<p>Mehmet Nurettin ÖZ Sakarya Şh. Eysel Çankaya Şh. Eysel Vize Tarihi: 04/08/2011 E-Adresi: Emekli Cad. No:616 Kızılkaya-ANKARA Tel: 0312) 422 93 76</p>
<p>İsmail ACAR Em. İ.Ş. AB. (1947-56) Çankaya Şh. Eysel Vize Tarihi: 12/06/2011 E-Adresi: 60 Sok. No:147 Emekli-ANKARA Tel: 0312) 222 35 48</p>	<p>H. Ferið DEVELEKÇİ Em. İ.Ş. K.İ. AB. (1940-21) Konya Şh. Eysel Vize Tarihi: 13/06/2011 E-Adresi: M. Paşa Cad. No:205/9 Konya-İZMİR Tel: 0312) 281 41 90</p>
<p>Hüseyin BASARCAN Em. P. K.İ. AB. (1940-20) Konya Şh. Eysel Vize Tarihi: 22/06/2011 E-Adresi: Bulvarı Çelebi Bulvarı No:178 Konya-İZMİR Tel: 0312) 361 90 48</p>	<p>Hüseyin Menteş SELİ Em. İ.Ş. K.İ. AB. (1942-11) Konya Şh. Eysel Vize Tarihi: 04/07/2011 E-Adresi: Hürriyet Çarşı Mah. Tunalıbaşı Sok. No:12 Kağıthane Fahri-İSTANBUL Tel: 0312) 534 64 66</p>
<p>Mehmet ÖPÜKARAN Em. P. K.İ. AB. (1953-5) Konya Şh. Eysel Vize Tarihi: 28/08/2011 E-Adresi: Akıncı Bulvarı Sankat Mah. İstasyon Cad. An. Kemal Çelebi Apt. No:27 D.5 Konya-BAKIRÇEVRE</p>	<p>Bayram AKMETE Em. P. K.İ. AB. (1915-17) Çankaya Şh. Eysel Vize Tarihi: 17/06/2011 E-Adresi: Çarşı Cad. Ömer Seyit Sok. No:911 Marmara-ANKARA Tel: 0312) 221 92 23</p>

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Canal ALCAN E.İS.İT.İB.İ. 1952 YIL KARADİĞİZ İLİ, ÜZÜMLÜ DAĞI By Address: Cumhuriyet Çiğdem Sok. No: 60/19 Blok 5/5 BASKIRI - İSTANBUL TEL: 0212 288 87 55	Emrah YARHAN E.İS.İT.İB.İ. 1952 YIL KARADİĞİZ İLİ, ÜZÜMLÜ DAĞI By Address: Cumhuriyet Çiğdem Sok. No: 60/19 Blok 5/5 BASKIRI - İSTANBUL TEL: 0212 288 87 55	Süleyman KIZILTUĞ E.İS.İT.İB.İ. 1952 YIL KARADİĞİZ İLİ, ÜZÜMLÜ DAĞI By Address: Cumhuriyet Çiğdem Sok. No: 60/19 Blok 5/5 BASKIRI - İSTANBUL TEL: 0212 288 87 55	Özgür SOYKAN E.İS.İT.İB.İ. 1952 YIL KARADİĞİZ İLİ, ÜZÜMLÜ DAĞI By Address: Cumhuriyet Çiğdem Sok. No: 60/19 Blok 5/5 BASKIRI - İSTANBUL TEL: 0212 288 87 55	Ö. Seyfettin BEYAZIL E.İS.İT.İB.İ. 1952 YIL KARADİĞİZ İLİ, ÜZÜMLÜ DAĞI By Address: Cumhuriyet Çiğdem Sok. No: 60/19 Blok 5/5 BASKIRI - İSTANBUL TEL: 0212 288 87 55	Tayyib KAYA E.İS.İT.İB.İ. 1952 YIL KARADİĞİZ İLİ, ÜZÜMLÜ DAĞI By Address: Cumhuriyet Çiğdem Sok. No: 60/19 Blok 5/5 BASKIRI - İSTANBUL TEL: 0212 288 87 55
Emrah ALTINEL E.İS.İT.İB.İ. 1952 YIL KARADİĞİZ İLİ, ÜZÜMLÜ DAĞI By Address: Cumhuriyet Çiğdem Sok. No: 60/19 Blok 5/5 BASKIRI - İSTANBUL TEL: 0212 288 87 55	A. İhsan ÖZKER E.İS.İT.İB.İ. 1952 YIL KARADİĞİZ İLİ, ÜZÜMLÜ DAĞI By Address: Cumhuriyet Çiğdem Sok. No: 60/19 Blok 5/5 BASKIRI - İSTANBUL TEL: 0212 288 87 55	Halil İZZET E.İS.İT.İB.İ. 1952 YIL KARADİĞİZ İLİ, ÜZÜMLÜ DAĞI By Address: Cumhuriyet Çiğdem Sok. No: 60/19 Blok 5/5 BASKIRI - İSTANBUL TEL: 0212 288 87 55	Fahri ALYARAK E.İS.İT.İB.İ. 1952 YIL KARADİĞİZ İLİ, ÜZÜMLÜ DAĞI By Address: Cumhuriyet Çiğdem Sok. No: 60/19 Blok 5/5 BASKIRI - İSTANBUL TEL: 0212 288 87 55	A. Pınarhan ÖZEL E.İS.İT.İB.İ. 1952 YIL KARADİĞİZ İLİ, ÜZÜMLÜ DAĞI By Address: Cumhuriyet Çiğdem Sok. No: 60/19 Blok 5/5 BASKIRI - İSTANBUL TEL: 0212 288 87 55	

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Faatiha DORALP Evl. Top. Kat. K.İ. A.Ş. (1993-41) Çankaya Şh. Üyesi Yolcu Tarih: 22/09/2010 Ev Adresi: Bahçelievler Sok. No:41/22 Dışkapı Apt. Çankaya - ANKARA Tel: 0312 439 81 13	Ahmet Yılmaz YILDIRMAZ Evl. Top. Kat. K.İ. A.Ş. (1993-33) Kadıköy Şh. Üyesi Yolcu Tarih: 11/09/2010 Ev Adresi: Çarşıyaka, İsmet Paşa Sok. Etiler Apt. No:111 Kadıköy - İSTANBUL Tel: 0212 367 11 66
Ayş ERER Evl. P. K.İ. A.Ş. (1948-34) Kadıköy Şh. Üyesi Yolcu Tarih: 11/09/2010 Ev Adresi: Çankaya, Çeşme Yolu Sakarya Cad. Kat: No: No: 1/10 Kadıköy - İSTANBUL Tel: 0212 36 27 24	AŞ SAYMAN Evl. Top. Kat. K.İ. A.Ş. (1993-41) Kadıköy Şh. Üyesi Yolcu Tarih: 23/09/2010 Ev Adresi: Çankaya, Çeşme Yolu Sakarya Cad. Kat: No: No: 1/10 Kadıköy - İSTANBUL Tel: 0212 36 27 24
Özmen Mustafa YATAR Evl. Top. Kat. K.İ. A.Ş. (1993-41) Kadıköy Şh. Üyesi Yolcu Tarih: 27/09/2010 Ev Adresi: Hürriyet İC. Çeşme Yolu D 02/02 No: 1111 Çeşme Apt. Kadıköy - İSTANBUL Tel: 0212 36 08 08	Görel ERONC Evl. Şh. A.Ş. (1960) Anadoluy Şh. Üyesi Yolcu Tarih: 04/09/2010 Ev Adresi: Zambak Mah. 199 Sok. A Blok Apt. D:2 No:2 ANTALYA Tel: 0242 311 89 13

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Kağan YÜCEL Sakay Ege Kadıköy Şh. Üyesi Yolcu Tarih: 10/09/2010 Ev Adresi: Çankaya, Kavutlar Sok. Kavutlar Cad. Çeşme Sok. No: 1/6 Kadıköy - İSTANBUL Tel: 0212 347 82 01	Selin ESENÖRÜK Evl. P. K.İ. A.Ş. (1943-41) Beşiktaş Şh. Üyesi Yolcu Tarih: 04/09/2010 Ev Adresi: Sıhhiye, 21. ve 22. Blok D 8 Katlısı - İSTANBUL Tel: 0212 281 37 97	Sahit ADAY Evl. P. K.İ. A.Ş. (1973-70) Lidyalıgözü Şh. Üyesi Yolcu Tarih: 04/09/2010 Ev Adresi: Beşiktaş Mah. 2. Avcı Sok. No: 2/10 LİDİYALIGÖZÜ - İSTANBUL Tel: 0212 435 30 23	Kemal Şahin ANSOY Evl. Şh. A.Ş. (1964-30) Beşiktaş Şh. Üyesi Yolcu Tarih: 04/09/2010 Ev Adresi: Çankaya, Bahçelievler Cad. Çeşme Sok. No: 2/10 İstanbul - ANKARA Tel: 0212 435 30 23
Faatiha NARİNG Evl. Şh. A.Ş. (1993-31) Kadıköy Şh. Üyesi Yolcu Tarih: 14/09/2010 Ev Adresi: Yıldırım Park Mah. Nispetiye Sok. Yıldırım Sok. 2. Blok D:2 Katlısı - İSTANBUL Tel: 0212 642 96 73	Ümrali Gülsüm DOĞUŞ Sakay Ege Beşiktaş Şh. Üyesi Yolcu Tarih: 25/09/2010 Ev Adresi: Beşiktaş, Sakarya Bulvarı No: 59/14 Katlısı Beşiktaş - İSTANBUL Tel: 0212 225 30 10	Hasan Ergün ERTOĐUK Evl. P. K.İ. A.Ş. (1941-38) Pnövelik Şh. Üyesi Yolcu Tarih: 10/09/2010 Ev Adresi: Bahçelievler Cad. Sakarya Apt. No: 41/14 Katlısı Kadıköy - İSTANBUL Tel: 0212 368 11 80	A. Mihail ÖZTEKİN Evl. P. K.İ. A.Ş. (1993-40) Kızılay Şh. Üyesi Yolcu Tarih: 10/09/2010 Ev Adresi: Sıhhiye, 21. ve 22. Blok D 8 Katlısı - İSTANBUL Tel: 0212 281 43 49
Mithat ALPARTUN Sakay Ege Beşiktaş Şh. Üyesi Yolcu Tarih: 20/09/2010 Ev Adresi: Yıldırım Park Mah. Nispetiye Sok. Çeşme Sok. No: 1/6 Kat: 2 Katlısı - İSTANBUL Tel: 0212 357 43 33	Ayşe KURT Sakay Ege Çankaya Şh. Üyesi Yolcu Tarih: 20/09/2010 Ev Adresi: Tamer Cad. No: 1/7 Kadıköy - ANKARA Tel: 0312 425 67 08	Sadrettin TEMEL Evl. Top. Kat. K.İ. A.Ş. (1990-23) Çankaya Şh. Üyesi Yolcu Tarih: 10/09/2010 Ev Adresi: Yıldırım Park Mah. 2. Avcı Sok. No: 2/10 LİDİYALIGÖZÜ - İSTANBUL Tel: 0212 634 13 34	Fevzi DURAL Evl. Şh. A.Ş. (1960-24) Çankaya Şh. Üyesi Yolcu Tarih: 04/09/2010 Ev Adresi: Yıldırım Park Mah. No: 7/4 Çeşme Sok. No: 2/10 Kadıköy - ANKARA Tel: 0212 338 13 06
Kaya ERGENC Evl. Şh. A.Ş. (1993-41) Çankaya Şh. Üyesi Yolcu Tarih: 20/09/2010 Ev Adresi: Yıldırım Park Mah. No: 1/6 Kat: 2 Katlısı - ANKARA Tel: 0312 338 43 33	İbrahim BARANKUL Evl. P. K.İ. A.Ş. (1948-34) Beşiktaş Şh. Üyesi Yolcu Tarih: 20/09/2010 Ev Adresi: Beşiktaş, Çankaya Bulvarı No: 59/14 Katlısı Beşiktaş - ANKARA Tel: 0212 225 30 10	Ehrem ECE Evl. P. K.İ. A.Ş. (1993-40) Çankaya Şh. Üyesi Yolcu Tarih: 20/09/2010 Ev Adresi: Çankaya Sok. Mah. No: 2 No: 2/10 Katlısı - ANKARA Tel: 0312 319 74 42	Canil PARLAYAN Evl. Şh. A.Ş. (1993-27) Çankaya Şh. Üyesi Yolcu Tarih: 20/09/2010 Ev Adresi: Yıldırım Park Mah. No: 7/4 Çeşme Sok. No: 2/10 Kadıköy - ANKARA Tel: 0212 338 43 33

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<p>Tuna KAM Etn. İst. Öğr. Ynl. (1963-409) Paralel Şb. Üyesi Yöke Tarih: 27/11/2010 Ev Adresi: Elm. Mah. Çiğdem Sok. Marm. Apt. No:22 C-2 Pazariçi 067400015 Tel: 0312 328 5271</p>		<p>Hüsnü TAZELER Etn.İst. İkt. İkt.İst. (1959-51) Çankaya Şb. Üyesi Yöke Tarih: 28/11/2010 Ev Adresi: Elm. Mah. Çiğdem Sok. No:611 A Apt. No: ANKARA Tel: 0312 426 41 72</p>	
<p>Hali DOĞANAY Etn. İkt. İkt. Adı (1947 - 35) Bağcıbaşı Şb. Üyesi Yöke Tarih: 28/11/2010 Ev Adresi: Marmar. Evleri Q1 B Blok D3 Katman: BEYANNUK Tel: 0312 472 23 92</p>		<p>Rasim ABRONAZ Etn.İst. İkt. Adı (1954-18) Çankaya Şb. Üyesi Yöke Tarih: 28/11/2010 Ev Adresi: Çiğdem Sok. 3. Blok No:32 Çankaya - ANKARA Tel:0312 442 36 25</p>	
<p>Ömer BİLİLELİ Etn.İst. Adı (1961-22) Yıldız Şb. Üyesi Yöke Tarih: 02/12/2010 Ev Adresi: Kurum Mah. 590 Sok. Oyuk Yolu No:69 ÇAYIROVA ANKARA Tel:0312 241 23 38</p>		<p>Ali Talat YOKUŞOĞLU Etn.İst. Ynl. (1955) Dutlu Şb. Üyesi Yöke Tarih: 02/12/2010 Ev Adresi: Kurum Mah. Malk. Sok. Salsarınçık Apt. No:563 B0211 Tel:0312 211 48 83</p>	
<p>Ali Hikmet ÖTOĞEN Etn.İst.İst. Anıttepe Şb. Üyesi Yöke Tarih: 08/12/2010 Ev Adresi: Baharınca Çiçeği Cad. Yılmaz Sok. B Blok No:22 AŞTİALTA Tel:0312 322 87 15</p>		<p>Adil AÇAR Etn.İst. Adı (1942-14) Çankaya Şb. Üyesi Yöke Tarih: 10/12/2010 Ev Adresi: Marmar Sok. Üstü Apt. No:2013 A Apt. No: ANKARA Tel:0312 426 0538</p>	
<p>Subhanî DEMİRCAN Etn.İst. Bornova Şb. Üyesi Yöke Tarih: 11/12/2010 Ev Adresi: 7066 Sk. No:477 Eğilim Apt. Pendik Mah. Büyükd. 22A08 Tel:0312 349 48 13</p>		<p>Mehmet Ramaz ERDEN Etn.İst. İkt. Adı (1947-040) Çankaya Şb. Üyesi Yöke Tarih: 12/12/2010 Ev Adresi: Elm. Sok. Çiğdem Apt. No: 2017 E-4 Blok No: ANKARA Tel:0312 431 99 22</p>	
<p>Fuat ÇOĞUN Etn. İst. Teğm. (1942 9 761) Çankaya Şb. Üyesi Yöke Tarih: 08/12/2010 Ev Adresi: TSK. Özel Bulvarı Ev. 1426 No:106 Bulvarı:ANKARA Tel:0312 412 56 38</p>		<p>Enel BENLİ Etn.İst. İkt. Adı (1962-26) Çankaya Şb. Üyesi Yöke Tarih: 21/12/2010 Ev Adresi: Oyuk Sok. No:2325 Çankaya - ANKARA Tel:0312 442 66 24</p>	

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